

Australian Research Data Commons

PIDs Implementation Guide for Institutions

Australian National Persistent Identifier Strategy

Developed by the Institutions Stakeholder Action Group

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Preamble and Audience

This document, the PIDs Implementation Guide, has been developed and reviewed by members of the Institutions Stakeholder Action Group of the Australian National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategy¹. It is intended for operational managers, implementers, and business process owners as a shared resource in developing their own technical implementation plans. As a community shared and community developed resource, this document includes recommendations for future joint-stakeholder work and is expected to evolve. The document includes the call for a statement to research information management system vendors, and also includes a number of “recipes” for PID enabled areas that collate advice and recommendations for each area. Where possible the recipes also indicate what essential PIDs are involved in each area, what are the significant use cases, key quality interventions, key decisions that will need to be made, and key system capabilities that will be required.

This document is designed to complement a number of other resources² developed by the Institutional Stakeholder Action Group. An important resource is the PID Value Proposition Resource³ which outlines a number of value proposition scenarios for institutions. This is an introduction to the PID ecosystem, it provides high-level guidance on determining the context dependent value propositions for implementing PIDs in an institution, and suggests business functions that can be more PID enabled. Another resource is the PID Capability & Maturity Model⁴ which aids organisations in assessing existing organisational maturity, in prioritising good foundations, and advises on essential resources and support. The capability maturity model provides a more systemic organisational overview of the target state that might be achieved, the range of areas and capabilities involved, and the benefits that can be realised in a range of areas. For those intending to develop or lead organisational plans or programs of PID improvements, be sure to also read the PID Capability & Maturity Model.

Acknowledgements

Working Group:

Melroy Almeida, Australian Access Federation. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3522-7849>

Kate Croker, University of Western Australia. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5290-6662>

Gerry Devine, University of New South Wales. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0074-112X>

Matthias Liffers, ARDC. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3639-2080>

Siobhann McCafferty, ARDC. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2491-0995>

¹ The 2024 Australian National Persistent Identifier (PID) Strategy and Roadmap.

<https://ardc.edu.au/project/australian-national-persistent-identifier-pid-strategy-and-roadmap/>

² ARDC, “Implement PIDs at your organisation (Accessing PID services)”, accessed 2025.

<https://pidroadmap.ardc.edu.au/pids/implement-pids-at-your-organisation>

ARDC, “Creating the National Collaborative Roadmap” (institution examples etc.), accessed 2025.

<https://pidroadmap.ardc.edu.au/pids/action-plans>

³ Australian PID Strategy Institutions Stakeholder Group, “PID Value Proposition Resource”.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18383260>

⁴ Australian PID Strategy Institutions Stakeholder Group, “PIDs Capability & Maturity Model”.

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Natasha Simons, ARDC. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0635-1998>

Jackie Stevens, Notre Dame University. <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0950-9343>

Harko Werkman, University of Tasmania. <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5603-5024>

Tania Wilmann, James Cook University. (co-chair) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9048-6395>

Lyle Winton, ARDC. (co-chair) <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3049-1221>

Scope, initial input, review and feedback were provided by members of the [Institutions Stakeholder Advisory Group](#) of the Australian National Persistence Identifier Strategy.

Towards a Statement for Vendors

The Implementation Guide working group (a subset of the Institutional Stakeholder Action Group) identified the need for developing platform integrations and in particular working with vendors to make PIDs possible. The working group recommends a consolidated statement be developed that outlines what is expected from a “PID ready platform”, intended to guide and encourage platform vendors to improve their support for, and integration with, PIDs. The opportunity exists to develop a shared national statement for institutions to use when engaging and advocating with vendors. Such a statement should:

- be a “Call to Action” and should synchronise across interested focus groups
- consider what is feasible to ask a vendor and what’s not.

Recommendation to Institutional Stakeholder Action Group: The focus group prioritised the need for work on platforms and in particular recommends working with vendors to make PIDs possible. We recommend that this work continues independently, and that a shared National Statement for Vendors be completed as a separate document.

Specific “Vendor Considerations” may be indicated in each of the Recipes below, and aspects of these, identified specific PID, and/or system actions and pain-points, may become part of a statement to vendors.

Further work is required to understand and/or define what type of platforms are typically suited to managing or integrating with different types of PIDs, e.g. repositories and research output PIDs, instrument PIDs, typical RIMS/CRIS system PIDs. The working group notes that managing PIDs from different types of systems is possible, and likely in any larger organisation.

Where possible the National PID Strategy implementers and Stakeholder Action Groups (institutions, funders, and NCRIS) are encouraged to share links to existing checklists, and how these support the choice of PID ready vendors.

A “PID-ready platform” should have a place to record and/or add PIDs. Specifically it should:

- Integrate or record ORCID for researchers
- Integrate or record ROR for organisations
- Integrate or record DOI for publications, datasets, instruments, grants etc
- Integrate or record RAiD for projects

A PID-ready platform should facilitate linking of records by the PID. For example, a grant record with a DOI should be able to be linked to the staff awarded the grant, outputs from the grant, instruments used and an overarching project.

A PID ready platform, where relevant and if a potential primary source of information, should be able to mint and manage PIDs and PID metadata, for example Elements or Pure and instrument PIDs.

PID Recipes

Getting Started

To assist in introduction and implementation of specific PIDs we have created a ‘recipe’ for a number of PID enabled areas to collate advice and recommendations. Most will outline key use cases for implementation, any specific governance or process decisions that may need to be made by your institution, and any quality and system considerations.

Some PIDs are generated by external organisations and may only need recording or integration with your systems, whilst PIDs that are generated by the institution or organisation will need to capture, store and maintain metadata about the PID.

PIDs such as DOIs require a place to store metadata about what they identify, or require a webpage URL where the PID will resolve to. Potential system types for storing PIDs and/or PID metadata are outlined in the recipe for each PID. PIDs can become crucial identifiers within enterprise systems, and PID metadata can become a crucial source of external information, but they are seldom the primary store of metadata for PIDs that are generated and maintained by the institution.

We recommend reading the metadata schema for the PID you are interested in to ensure minimum data is captured, however to ensure rich data, capture and record as much information as possible.

Additionally, before PID implementation, consider how your systems can talk to one another to enable reuse and/or linking of PIDs wherever possible.

Recipe - Facility and Organisation PIDs, and ROR

Recommendation to Institutional Stakeholder Action Group: Feedback and a more sophisticated conversation with ROR is needed. Some things are problematic for the National PID Strategy, such as institutional oversight/workflow over their own RORs.

ROR is a PID and a global registry for identifying and finding research organisations. It can be used to link an organisation to related entities such as its researchers, projects, instruments and research outputs.

In Australia it is appropriate for a top level entity such as a University or national facility to have a ROR. Other research entities that have their own public branding (e.g. NCRIS facilities, Centres of Excellence, Co-operative Research Centres, Institutes) may also have a ROR.

ROR is operated as a community-led, collaborative initiative by California Digital Library, Crossref, and DataCite and was launched in 2019. It is **recommended** that institutions use ROR as their persistent identifier for organisations.

Quality Interventions

Each institution should have a **nominated person** at the institution who is responsible for monitoring their institution's RORs. We **recommend** this be the same as the ORCID admin contact at that institution.

Each institution's nominated contact should check their ROR entry. ROR supports parent-child relationships so this should include checking any child organisations and related organisations. Each institution should have a single ROR, which encompasses all campuses. The only exception is for overseas campuses which may operate as separate entities.

ROR's may be created for Centres of Excellence, Co-operative Research Centres or Institutes that are associated with your Institution, but have their own public branding. The ROR for these entities should be associated with the overarching Institution.

Key Use Cases

RORs are used by the organisation to identify collaborations with external organisations. Institutions should adopt best practice and record organisation RORs for collaborators and contributors external to the organisation. Ideally, the ROR will be associated with a person's ORCID and therefore be provided automatically, however this may not always be the case.

Key Decisions

A ROR will not be suitable or available for all external collaborators. Institutions will need to decide how to track or monitor collaborations with organisations that don't have a ROR and whether another identifier (e.g. Scopus organisation ID, institutional identifier, ABN etc) will be used.

System Capabilities

Systems that may record ROR include

- Profile management systems
- Research Information Management Systems (RIMS) or Current Research Information Systems (CRIS)
- Repositories
- Grant Management Systems

If your system includes records about research organisations or funders, you should link each one to a ROR identifier—either by integrating with the ROR API or by uploading the official ROR spreadsheet. (Assistance with how to ask your vendor to include or link to ROR will be available via the Vendor Statement.)

Where your institution makes data available via an API or other delivery mechanisms, include ROR IDs for all organisations if available, to support standardised and interoperable data use.

Vendor Considerations

- Allow organisational records within record management systems to be associated with a ROR, either via the ROR API or via the official spreadsheet.
- Vendors should align ROR's with any vendor specific ID's in their system so that institutions can consume the ROR rather than match the vendor specific ID with the ROR.

Recipe - Researcher Profiles and ORCID

ORCID connects researchers to their research contributions across time, discipline and affiliation. The key driver is having visible and appropriate attribution and recognition of researchers' contributions, their institutional affiliations, and this information being accurate and available via their ORCID record. Institutions must set the expectation that all research staff and students have an ORCID and that ORCID records are largely reusable (by default not set to 'private').

Consider the researcher's perspective, as it is important to promote a number of key messages. ORCID promotes a researcher's work, achievements, institution, acknowledges funders and contributors, and helps ensure researchers are appropriately attributed. Visibility enhances a researcher's reputation and can lead to future opportunities. Institutionally verified ORCID information will increasingly save researchers time and build trust in the researcher's profile. An ORCID establishes a record of a researcher's full career profile, independent of current institution, and will be valuable in all future collaborations, affiliations and positions.

It is recommended that the institutions, at the very least, collect only authenticated ORCIDs (never manually entered, ensuring definitive links), and that an integrated system at the institution will write verified information back into an ORCID record. But beyond this, streamlining administration should occur where appropriate by using information read from an ORCID record. The writing of verified information back into an ORCID record ensures trust markers, and provides efficiencies and confidence in the use of the ORCID information for future grant applications, affiliations, collaborations, publications and for other downstream uses.

Essential PIDs

ORCIDs are the essential public identifier and form a visible register of a researcher's profile, and ORCIDs are designed to recognise a researcher's contributions over time, across disciplines and employment changes.

RORs are also essential to this recipe. An institution should be writing an employment and/or education assertion into each researcher's ORCID record, which must include known dates and the institution's ROR. This is necessary to support both the National PID Strategy and institutions in reporting and benchmarking. Other initiatives, such as Research Link Australia, require this to accurately map Australia's research capability and to promote researchers to industry.

Vendor Considerations: Research systems that hold information that can be written to ORCID records should also support writing institutional employment/education affiliation with start and end dates assertions to ORCID.

Appropriate attribution for researchers requires that records of their research are associated with their ORCID. This goes beyond ORCID in institutional systems, and requires that researchers provide their ORCID when publishing, creating traditional published outputs, when creating/registering other research artefacts (sometimes referred to as non-traditional or creative practice artefacts), and in association with grants, funding, projects and activities. So by association, other PIDs such as RAIDs, DOIs and IGSNs should appropriately capture these ORCIDs and attribute a researcher by including their ORCID.

Key Use Cases

The successful implementation of ORCID involves two essential business processes (referred to below as use case 0 and 1) which are the foundations of ORCID integration and follows ORCID best practices. And the subsequent use cases (A, B, C, D) are typical ways that institutions might approach their ORCID integration with existing systems.

Use Case 0 - the foundation:

Onboarding researchers is the foundation use-case of ORCID workflows at institutions. All researchers must provide their ORCID to their institutions to be recorded in a central system. If a researcher or research student does not already have an ORCID, the institution should assist or guide the researcher in creating an ORCID (via a system or user support, whatever is most efficient, see use case 1).^{5, 6} Ideally ensure that researchers can create an ORCID as part of the registration process from within the central system interface. This will ensure a streamlined experience and the ORCID will be integrated upon creation. Recommendations are that:

- All researchers and research students in an organisation should have an ORCID ID. Institutions must set the expectation that all research staff and students have an ORCID, or that having ORCID should be the default situation, unless there are reasons for opting-out.
- The institution should collect only authenticated ORCID IDs, that is, IDs that have been verified by the owner who has authenticated using the ORCID system. Institutions should not accept IDs that have been manually entered by a researcher or staff.⁷
- Institutions should strongly recommend their researchers' ORCID account settings include "Visibility" being set to "Everyone" or at least "Trusted Organizations". Researchers can be assured that even with visibility set to "Everyone" by default, they still have the option to set specific records to private or visible only to trusted parties. (If trusted parties access is chosen, records can be seen by parties or organisations whom the user has granted access to their ORCID record, requiring explicit permission on the user's part.)
- Systems that make available aspects of a researcher's profile should also provide their associated ORCID ID, and this should include access to profile information via machine/API access (such as OAI-PMH, HTML meta tags, JSON-LD) and via any public presentations such as web pages (researcher profile pages, repository items and authors). It is important to ensure that ORCIDs are being populated in systems that already allow for ORCIDs.

⁵ ORCID Documentation - Workflows - Employment. <https://info.orcid.org/documentation/workflows/employment-workflow/>

⁶ ORCID Documentation - Workflows - Education. <https://info.orcid.org/documentation/workflows/education-workflow/>

⁷ ORCID Integration Best Practice. <https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-best-practices/>

- Institutions should consider leveraging ORCID information, for onboarding new researchers and perhaps other processes, by collecting/importing information from ORCID records rather than requiring users to provide historical profile information.

Use Case 1 - establishing ORCID integration:

An institution should have at least one system/process that integrates with ORCID. The expectation is that the institution will read information from an ORCID record, and also write verified information back into an ORCID record. Doing so increases trust markers within the researcher's ORCID record, providing efficiencies and confidence in the use of the ORCID metadata downstream (e.g. grant applications, future affiliations, collaborations, publications). Recommendations are:

- Organisations should have at least one system that is integrated with ORCID. This involves researchers following a procedure within the integrated systems, to allow reading and writing of the ORCID record. The user authenticates with their ORCID IDs as part of this procedure, through the OAUTH API process, and the system obtains permission to read and/or write to their ORCID record.⁸ (Technically each system needs to establish and record an OAuth-2 token from the ORCID system for each user. Each token only relates to one user who has authorised that system, which has registered as an API client, ensuring their ORCID ID is authenticated and their ORCID account is connected for system access.)
- Organisations that collect researcher contributions either via research management systems, profile systems or institutional repositories, should write verified information into their researchers ORCID records via the API. Doing this will also increase trust markers in the researcher's ORCID record, increasing the level of assurance and providing confidence in the ORCID metadata downstream (e.g. grant applications, future affiliations, collaborations, publications).

Use Case scenario A - RIMS as point of truth:

In some institutions, the research information management system (RIMS) or research profile system will be considered the point of truth for a researcher's information. Typically in this scenario that system should be the main system chosen for Use Case 1 (ORCID integration) to read and write to ORCID records. This system is typically an aggregation of information such as repository/publisher metadata, grant information, and HR information. The system can be configured to push to and optionally pull from ORCID.⁹

Use Case scenario B - repository as point of truth:

In some institutions, the research repository is considered the point of truth, and should be chosen for Use Case 1 (ORCID integration) to read and write to ORCID records. Typical configuration is to push to

⁸ ORCID Documentation - Integration Best Practices. <https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-best-practices/>
ORCID Documentation - ORCID OAuth sign in guidelines.

<https://info.orcid.org/documentation/integration-guide/orcid-oauth-sign-in-guidelines/>

⁹ ORCID Documentation - Research Information Systems Integration Best Practice.

<https://info.orcid.org/research-information-systems/>

ORCID and optionally pull from ORCID.¹⁰ However, if the repository is not the sole point of truth see scenario C.

Use Case scenario C - multiple points of truth:

It is common for more than one system to be the point of truth, and each is required to integrate and write assertions to ORCID. Be aware this will generally require the researcher to integrate their ORCID with each system simply by granting system access permissions. However, an architecture is possible where there is one centralised ORCID integration (as is the case at CSIRO), and the application or client tokens are shared between multiple systems.¹¹

Use Case scenario D - collection via ORCID:

In addition to the other use cases, some institutions may decide that as part of regular reporting or collection of information, that certain information will be harvested from ORCID into their central systems for validation. This may be an attractive option for some researchers, as they can choose to keep ORCID up to date by integrating with other services, such as the Crossref ORCID Auto-update.¹² However, some institutions prefer workflows where records are collected by the institution first, often from external sources to reduce researcher data entry, before being validated and written to ORCID records. Institutions could use both methods or allow researchers to optionally harvest from their ORCID accounts, to support their regular collection.

Regardless of the pathways chosen, it's essential that organisations write verified records back to a researcher's ORCID records (see essential use case 1). The ORCID system will not present these as duplicate records in ORCID, if existing, but as multiple records on the same associated item. The primary example is publications, where an article may have been entered by the researcher, may have a source record from Crossref, and can still benefit from having a verified record from an institution.

Quality Interventions

ORCID information is required for Australian Research Council (ARC) grant applications, so quality is important, and institutions should encourage their researchers' to keep their ORCID information as complete and accurate as possible. Many institutions have regular or annual processes to ensure their researcher information (e.g. contributions to outputs, grants) is up to date centrally, so ensuring this information flows on to the researchers' ORCID records is the most practical approach. At the very least, the minimum metadata required needs to be available within the ORCID record.¹³

To clarify the recommended approach, it is not expected that researchers need to be more aware of minimum ORCID metadata, nor that accuracy and quality are solely their responsibility. What is required is that researchers have an ORCID, that this is captured and integrated within institutional systems, and that the institutional systems are able to write more complete and accurate information to ORCID, information that has been incrementally verified by institutional processes. A successful approach should set up researchers and the institution for reduced administrative burden. If verified information is

¹⁰ ORCID Documentation - Repository Systems Integration Best Practice. <https://info.orcid.org/repository-systems/>

¹¹ AAF ORCID Resources. <https://aaf.edu.au/orcid/resources/>

¹² Crossref's ORCID Auto-update. <https://www.crossref.org/community/orcid/>

¹³ ORCID Metadata support documentation. <https://support.orcid.org/hc/en-us/sections/360002501973-ORCID-Metadata>

increasingly available via ORCID records, then other institutions, collaborators, funding bodies, and publishers will not need to ask researchers for the same information again, and the information will not need to be re-verified. (This supports one of the key National PID Strategy objectives, the reduction of administrative burden, by reducing the time spent re-entering data, correcting manual data entry, and re-validating information, as well as ensuring more accurate and streamlined reporting.)

It is recommended, however, that clear guidance be made available to researchers regarding the importance of ORCID, and essential integrations with institutional systems, and how read and write functionality of that integration is expected to work. This guidance should provide the following answers and information:

- How frequently does the read/write update occur?
- Does the read/write process need to be instigated manually by the researcher (perhaps better for some RIMS products) or does it occur automatically when new content is added, updated and verified?
- Does the integration facilitate one-way or both-ways information sharing?
- Does the system allow for selection of only some data to be shared with ORCID? (Noting to the researcher that in this case they may need to update remaining data directly in ORCID.)
- Assurances that institutional information written to ORCID records will not duplicate any existing information, rather it adds institutional verification to the existing information, strengthening trust markers within the researcher's ORCID profile. So, for example, a researcher can safely continue to add publications to their ORCID profile (ideally using DOIs to reduce data entry), they are able to make specific records public/restricted, and information written by their institution will serve to verify publications. (Depending on an institution's integration, it should be clear if researcher added/updated information will be harvested by their institution systems.)
- An explanation of the importance of researchers providing their ORCID when creating traditional published outputs, when creating/registering other research artefacts (sometimes referred to as non-traditional or creative practice artefacts), and in association with grants, funding, projects and activities. (Systems outside of the institution may allow for providing an ORCID or authenticating an ORCID to associate with a user's account.)

Key Decisions

By considering the use cases above, an institution should determine which systems hold point-of-truth information and which are integrated with ORCID.

Determine via which communication channels or processes key messaging around ORCID is provided, with links to clear guidance and services or support. Institutions must set the expectation that all research staff and students have an ORCID, that their ORCID have the default visibility setting of "Everyone" (or at least "Trusted parties"), and that their ORCID must be integrated within certain institutional systems.

Reviewing the quality interventions above, should help in developing key messages on how ORCID is part of the regular information process, how it sets up researchers and the institution for reduced administrative burden, and what guidance and assurances you may need to provide.

System Capabilities

Many research management systems and repositories will be capable of having an ORCID integration. ORCID has a certified service provider list that includes systems meeting ORCID's best practices and that allow for writing to researchers' ORCID records.¹⁴

For in house development see the "ORCID-Source" repository on github, a set of web apps and libraries.¹⁵ ORCID provides documentation including workflows, best practices, guides, tutorials and resources.¹⁶

ORCID is a mature and internationally recognised system that many systems should already be configured to recognise. So be sure to consider the population of ORCID IDs in systems that allow for it, and especially in systems that present aspects of a researcher's activities online, e.g. profile systems, expert directories, projects and funded activities, repositories of research outputs, and author pages. This will help researchers and their collaborators to properly recognise and attribute an institution's researcher contributions and the institution itself (if employment or education association is being properly written to the researcher's ORCID record). This will also help build local and global awareness that ORCID IDs should be provided wherever possible in local and external systems. The institution should also ensure that ORCID IDs are being populated via any existing machine-readable and API access, e.g. OAI-PMH, HTML meta tags, JSON-LD.

Vendor Considerations: Systems must establish a link to ORCID that will write new information whenever a record is created or updated by the institution. Avoid where possible the need for manual updates. This reduces administrative burden for researchers and maintains accurate, up to date records.

Recipe - Infrastructure, Facilities, Platforms and Instruments

The ability to assign globally unique and persistent identifiers to research instrumentation (laboratory equipment, environmental sensors, etc.) is critical for supporting the integrity and reproducibility of the research these instruments enable. It also provides a foundation for tracking and assessing the impact of research infrastructure over time.

For this recipe instrument will be used as a generic term to refer to a piece of infrastructure, platform or equipment that is used to support research. The assignment of unique identifiers, and decisions about what instruments will be assigned identifiers will be the responsibility of the institution or organisation that houses the instrument.

¹⁴ ORCID Certified Service Providers List.

<https://info.orcid.org/vendors-and-service-providers/orcid-certified-service-providers-list/>

¹⁵ ORCID-Source repository, by ORCID on GitHub. <https://github.com/ORCID/ORCID-Source>

¹⁶ ORCID Documentation. <https://info.orcid.org/documentation/>

Metadata describing instruments should follow the PIDInst schema.¹⁷ Additional guidance can also be found in the Australasian Best practices for Instrument Identifiers.¹⁸

Related PIDs

Each DOI provider (such as CrossRef or DataCite) have their own metadata schema associated with the DOI service they offer. In the case of research instruments, DataCite have adapted the DOI metadata schema to support the PIDINST recommended metadata fields.

DOI: resourceTypeGeneral=Instrument

- **Created:** As the primary PID of the instrument
- Potentially associated to other PIDs given the possible hierarchical structure of instrumentation (instruments can be made up of several existing, PID-allocated, smaller instruments, etc)

DOI: datasets, grants, grey literature, publications

- **Consumed:** Where known, downstream outputs of the instrument (dataset DOIs, journal article DOIs, etc) can be included directly within the metadata of the instrument to indicate association
- **Consumed** as auxiliary documentation (technical reports, journal articles, etc documenting the makeup and implementation of an instrument)
- **Consumed** as grant/funding information (i.e. what funded the instrument implementation/funds its ongoing support etc.)
- **Contributed to** DOI metadata of datasets (source field etc.)

Connections between instruments and the data they collect can be indicated using RelatedIdentifiers with the relationTypes IsCollectedBy and Collects¹⁹.

ORCID:

- **Consumed** to describe instrument owners/contacts/manufacturers (in the case of bespoke instrumentation etc.)
- **Contributed to** (in the case of individual/bespoke-created instrument)

ROR:

- **Consumed** as the 'hosting institution' and/or hosting facility, and potentially 'Manufacturer'

RAiD:

- **Contributed to** as the instrument which contributes to project results

¹⁷ PIDINST DataCite Cookbook. <https://docs.pidinst.org/en/latest/datacite-cookbook/index.html>

¹⁸ "Best Practices: PIDs for Instruments", Identifiers for Instruments in Australasia Community of Practice (i4iOZ). <https://zenodo.org/records/7759201>

¹⁹ DataCite metadata schema - IsCollectedBy & Collects.

<https://datacite-metadata-schema.readthedocs.io/en/4.5/appendices/appendix-1/relationType/#iscollectedby>

IGSN:

- **Contributes to:** in the case where an instrument collects or generates a research sample

Key Use Cases

While the following use cases are articulated as straightforward information capabilities, the resulting metadata automation and increased metadata access will support a more administratively efficient visibility of research capability, utilisation and return on investment.

Provenance: The ability to link a dataset (or other research output) to an instrument that was key in its creation will enhance the understanding, reproducibility, and integrity of that dataset.

Impact tracking: There is the requirement to track outputs from an instrument (datasets as well as research leading from those datasets) as a way to measure the impact of that instrument on the scientific process.

To inform booking or related systems: The existence of managed persistent identifiers would aid in the management of instrumentation-related systems - e.g. Instrument discovery portals, instrument booking systems.

To inform suitability of use: Metadata collected per instrument may aid identification of instrumentation suitable for an upcoming research venture.

Return On Investment: to indicate usage of instrument/s vs investment and relation to outputs

Quality Interventions

It is **recommended** that requests for new instrument PIDs will pass through a review body (whether Library or similar). In this case staff undertaking the review may need to upskill in recognising and ensuring good quality metadata associated with a research instrument.

Key Decisions

Creation of PIDs for instruments, and which instruments to create PIDs for will be determined by the institution.

System Capabilities

The institution may already have one or several systems which are associated with instruments which have specific functionality and collect specific metadata. The institution will need to determine which platform will act as the “source of truth” for the metadata that will relate to the PID.

Best practice suggests that the information, regardless of system, is owned and managed by the facility that houses the instrument or the acquisitions and asset management portfolio or similar.

When choosing a system, the capability of the system for reporting and/or reproducibility and the requirements of the institution should be considered. For example; do any specific settings and/or setup of the instrument need to be recorded as part of the PID.

Systems that could be considered to store PID instrument metadata may include:

- Institutional RIMS system
 - May already have some instrument recording/metadata capture functionality
 - May already be linked to or able to automatically generate DOI's
 - May already have functionality to link records (e.g. associate an instrument record with an output and/or grant)
 - May be able to create a publicly facing page about the instrument for the DOI to resolve to
 - Unlikely to have the specific metadata fields required for instruments
- Institutional Repository (where separate to the Institutional RIMS)
 - May need customisation to be able to record instrument metadata
 - Likely to already be connected to automatically generate DOI's
 - Already regarded as a source of truth for other information
 - May already have functionality to link records (e.g. associate an instrument record with an output and/or grant)
 - May be able to create a publicly facing page about the instrument for the DOI to resolve to
- Laboratory Management system and/or Instrument Booking System
 - May contain the detailed metadata required for the PID
 - May not be associated with a publicly facing webpage for the DOI to resolve to
 - Unlikely to be connected to automatically generate DOIs

Institutions may also consider linking systems, where for example the metadata is collected at instrument facility and this information is used to generate a record in the institutional RIMS or institutional repository which generates the PID.

Best practice will capture the linkage between instrument and a downstream output (e.g. directly generated dataset) both at the instrument record level (e.g. by technical/instrument staff) and at the output/dataset record level (e.g. by researchers identifying the instrument used to generate the current dataset being documented). This means that other institutional systems (e.g. RIMS, repository) should be able to support the association of instrument PIDs with records.

Institutional systems should be able to ingest API feeds from other records systems and associate other persistent identifiers with the relevant instrument. (e.g. if an instrument DOI is cited in a publication, this should be able to be identified and associated via the Scopus API, repository API or similar).

Institutional systems should be able to provide API feeds to other systems to allow association of instrument PIDs with data in other systems.

Vendor Considerations:

- Include fields for metadata associated with PIDs for instruments as standard in repository systems and research information management systems that include an equipment/facilities section

- Allow association of instrument PIDs with other data records (e.g. research outputs, datasets) via APIs and other machine readable information

Recipe - Project and Activity Tracking, and RAiD

Recommendation to Institutional Stakeholder Action Group: It is difficult to have a definitive institutional implementation guide for RAiD at this point. We have emerging practice only, as institutional learnings are quite recent and very few. Understanding or awareness of the benefits in the sector is limited, impeding uptake. This recipe should ensure interested adopters can be better acquainted with the elements involved. Therefore, this Recipe advises institutions on what they should be doing or discussing, rather than focusing on implementation. We also capture case studies from the University of Notre Dame Australia, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Australian government's National Environmental Science Partners (NESP). Additionally, RAiD functionality in commercially available RIMS is not yet established, requiring strong vendor engagement/encouragement.

RAiD Principle Value Proposition

The Research Activity Identifier (RAiD) is a relatively new ISO standard (23527:2022) for identifying research projects with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) as the ISO-appointed Registration Authority for the global RAiD system. The principal value proposition of RAiD for tracking research activity stems from its design as a centralised, interoperable, and open standard for describing and managing research projects. Its core value lies in creating a rich, updateable record or profile of a research project, providing a minimal set of information that not only describes the project but also captures associations with other PID-described entities such as funders, organizations, collaborators, tools, services, and data.

RAiD allows for comprehensive reporting on “connected things” (research institutions, researchers and contributors, funding, inputs and outputs, preceding and subsequent projects), enabling a deeper understanding of project impacts and outcomes that goes beyond what can be inferred solely from publications or grants. For institutions, RAiD offers a crucial capability to track projects effectively, serving as an institutional record that simplifies the aggregation, sharing, and reporting of project metadata, thereby reducing administrative burden and facilitating better strategic analysis and decision-making within the Australian research ecosystem.

While RAiD is available for use and is expanding rapidly on a global scale, Australian institutions have been slower in adoption, perhaps due to its novelty and a desire for confidence in local uptake. However, a widespread adoption RAiD has the potential to become a powerful tool for institutions, governments and other stakeholders. RAiD will enable insights into the downstream impacts of funded research, across multiple years and projects.

Preparing for RAiD

An institution is most likely to benefit from RAiD implementation when a level of maturity is reached on implementing and populating other priority PIDs. For example, an activity profile captures associated

PIDs (ORCID, ROR, DOI for outputs, instruments, and research funding) and primary metadata of a project (title, description, dates, subject). The adoption of RAiD can act as a catalyst to drive adoption of other priority PIDs.

The working group recommends institutions use the following key questions, both to gauge readiness for RAiD and to guide decisions during implementation.

- What is your institution's purpose for implementing RAiD? This will inform when to mint a RAiD, i.e. what actions prompt the generation of a RAiD, and what will the RAiD be attached to, and clarifies the institutional role in minting a RAiD. Is the catalyst the capability to track a project, or be the record of a project? Is it triggered by receipt of grant funding, approval of an Ethics Application, or generation of a Research Data Management Plan?
- Consider if RAiDs will be created for only a limited number of projects, e.g. high profile or complex collaborations.
- Consider how these RAiDs (and associated PIDs) will be used somewhere else, perhaps at another institution, or by a collaborator or stakeholder. Are there ways a RAiD can be made even more useful to others within your institution or to others across collaborations? These can make visible human readable connections, or may be used to visualise activities, or to aid in navigating a research network. In the case of multi-institution funding or collaborations how will you decide who generates the RAiD? Note that the ownership of RAiDs can be passed to other institutions if needed.
- What happens when a researcher leaves? Or if a project leaves the institution? (A degree of institutional recognition should remain.) Note that the ownership of RAiDs can be passed to other institutions.
- What are you trying to achieve by implementing RAiD? Consider which records matter most – a researcher's profile, research outputs and other artefacts, ethics, funding (internal, grants, contract), impact evidence - and whether RAiD could be part of a broader solution that connects them in a coherent history.
- Should RAiD be created manually by a central administration point, who can manage and curate RAiD metadata to ensure quality? Consider if researchers should be given ongoing access to the RAiD record to manage edits.
- Or should RAiD be created automatically via API? This will be dependent on the quality of the source metadata that researchers have contributed to, potentially metadata coming from systems such as a RDMP (research data management plans). Consider if you should give the researcher ongoing access to the RAiD record for curation, after creation, particularly if metadata in source systems is not often updated.
- Consider mandating training for those who have created a RAiD, administrators, or research maintainers. Suggested training could be implemented by systems providing alerts (e.g. RDMP) at the point of mint.

Key Use Cases

Tracking a large project over time: An institution generates a RAiD to track the work of a number of funded projects that are around a similar theme, for a similar stakeholder etc. Generating a RAiD allows the following:

- Individual funding records to be associated with the RAiD, tracking the entirety of the project funding
- All data and output records are associated with the larger project rather than just the smaller individual funded projects
- May allow the recording of research impacts or other information that is not relevant to one of the single funded projects but is relevant to the project overall

Tracking unfunded projects: Researchers may be undertaking projects that are not (yet) formally funded, but which are still generating research data and/or research outputs. For example, these may be related to pedagogy and teaching and are done as part of their funded position. Generating a RAiD allows the visibility of these projects and their associated outputs. It also shows what work may have been done on a project before funding is received.

Tracking individual projects: Institutions may wish to issue RAiDS for individual projects. These RAiDS may later be collated together under a larger project. This facilitates tracking of both inputs and outputs for each individually funded project as well as the overall project.

Recommendation to the Institutional Stakeholder Action Group: Members of the focus group would like to recommend the development of guiding principles about when to mint a RAiD, to ensure consistency. RAiD has the potential to be a powerful tool for institutions, governments and other stakeholders to gain insights into the systemic impact of funded research activities across multiple years and projects.

Recipe - Grants Management

Grants Management can capture the lifecycle of a request for funding through to the award of funding and associated responsibilities. This includes the searching for appropriate funding bodies and schemes, development of the application, including any internal review done by the organisation, submission to the funding body, assessment and, in some successful cases, award. Post-award management such as milestone reporting and variations is also included.

The processes involved in this cycle can intersect with the use of many different PIDs at different points of the cycle. It should be noted that this recipe does not need to be implemented in its entirety and can be used in parts. Whilst funding bodies external to institutions are responsible for crucial parts of the process, actions undertaken by institutions help facilitate all stages. For example, the ARC and NHMRC now rely on the provision of ORCIDs during the submission of funding applications, which is increasingly valuable to both funding bodies and institutions in linking high quality research and outputs.

Essential PIDs

- ORCID - should be **consumed** and **contributed to**
- ROR - should be **consumed**
- DOI for instruments/infrastructure - should be **consumed**

- DOI for funding - should be **consumed**, perhaps **created**
- RAiD - can be **created** or **contributed to**

Key Use Cases

Identify funding opportunities:

Aim - Deliver content that is relevant

Link ORCID to funding search databases (e.g. PivotRP or Funding Institutional) can facilitate discovery and notification of funding opportunities that match past publications, past awarded funding and listed research interests.

Submission of funding application - for approval at institution:

Aim - Capture metadata to guide institutional reporting and decision making

- Names of internal and external researchers entered on the grant should be associated with an ORCID, potentially via an ORCID search. This ensures that ongoing collaborations with external individuals can be tracked and removes duplicate data in the institution RIMS.
- Names of organisations or entities should be associated with a ROR. This allows for reporting to demonstrate ongoing engagement and removes duplicate data in the institution RIMS. Organisations or entities that are not suitable for a ROR should be associated with a unique identifier at the institution.
- Any instruments or infrastructure should be identified in the application with its associated PID. This allows the institution to monitor demand and intended use.

Submission of funding application - funding body interface:

Aim - Institutionally verified information, and overall reduction of manual data entry

While funding bodies are generally responsible for the submission process, actions undertaken by institutions help facilitate all parts of the process.

- Entering the ORCID of all researchers named on the grant should negate or greatly reduce the need for manually entering CV data. Ideally, the funder will have a high level of trust in the provided ORCID/CV data, provided the data has been assured by **institutions writing verified information into their researchers' ORCID records**. (See the Researcher Profile and ORCID Recipe above.)
- **Institutions should also be automatically populating the affiliation** of their researcher using the ROR linked to the ORCID record.

Award of funding:

Aim - To record identifiers to associate future research outcomes with funding to show benefit/impact

The Australian National PID Strategy recommends funders create DOIs for awarded funding, which will be the case for future ARC grants. While funding bodies may adopt different approaches to managing awarded funding, institutions can still ensure that related information is captured, linked and associated with that funding record.

- **Institutions should capture and record** persistent identifiers from awarded funding in the institutional RMS.
- Institutions continue to be responsible for providing any updated information to funding bodies, which should increasingly enable the update of associated PID metadata that funding bodies maintain. This might include grant DOIs and associate researcher ORCID records, for example.
- Institutions **may wish to create DOI's** for any funding awarded by the institution.
- The institution **may wish to create a RAiD** or associate this funding with an existing RAiD. If the funding is associated with multiple institutions, then it is recommended that the leading institution should create a RAiD.

Post-award management:

Aim - To ensure that post-award activities are recorded against the same record

- Use the grant persistent identifier for reference in all post-award changes or correspondence.
- Associate any research output PIDs (e.g. DOI for publications, other research artefacts, datasets) with the grant PID.
- Record any instrument or infrastructure use against the grant PID.
- If investigators or named personnel change throughout the period of the grant, associated PIDs will need updating (e.g. RAiD contributors, grant DOIs updated by the funder/institution as mentioned above, and related ORCID assertions will need to be written).

Quality Interventions

ORCID - accurate and maintained metadata is essential for accurately populating funding application systems.

- Where possible, ORCID should be linked with the institutional profile and integrated with the institution's research information system(s) so that verified information and updates are written to ORCID records.
- An ORCID should be provided to and mandated by the funder in order to apply for funding. (There may be cases where smaller funders are unable to process ORCIDs, for example industry funding and research contracts. Institutions **may wish to create a DOI where they are funding an activity and capture ORCIDs** for such funding.)
- Institutional onboarding of staff should ensure that researchers provide (and perhaps create) their authenticated ORCID, provide permission for the institution's ORCID-integrated system(s) to read and write to their ORCID records, and ultimately the ORCID will be visible via the institutional profile system.

ROR - accurate ROR's are essential for accurately populating affiliation information into the funding application system. They are also highly desired for accurate institutional reporting. RORs can also be assigned to the research funding agencies and linked to the grant DOI.

- Where possible, use either the ROR API or the downloaded database to populate RIMS with organisation identifiers.
- Ensure that new organisations created have an ROR.

Key Decisions

The following changes to governance and processes are recommended.

- Institutional onboarding should include
 - recording and/or creation of an ORCID for research staff
 - linking a staff members' ORCID to the institutional research information system(s)
 - Allowing content created in one system (RIMS/ORCID) to populate the other system
- Develop a process to assign a persistent local identifier to entities and organisations where a ROR is not available and/or appropriate
- Decide where the DOI for awarded funding should be recorded in institutional systems
- Decide whether the institution will mint DOI's for
 - Internal funding awarded by the institution
- Mandate that the DOI for awarded funding be recorded and a primary identifier used across all institutional systems e.g. finance, RIMS and reporting
- Develop a procedure for the generation and use of RAiDs and how awarded funding will be either assigned to or trigger the creation of a RAiD

System Capabilities

It is important to consider what existing systems are involved in grants management and what are their existing capabilities. A number of systems can support a degree of PID capture, perhaps some may support PID metadata management, but if not, there may be PID integration patterns that involve light-weight coupling to your information systems and the use of external PID tools. Consult with your vendor, national PID support staff, and potentially fellow institutions and PID stakeholders.

- Grant application and other research agency systems should have the capacity to link to ORCID

Vendor Considerations: that providers of systems to research agencies introduce the ability to connect to a researcher's ORCID and be able to deliver content relevant to the researcher based on ORCID data.

- Institutional RIMS
 - Record ORCID
 - Ideally, link to ORCID and have content updating between ORCID and the RIMS (see the ORCID recipe)
 - Record ROR
 - Ideally, link to ROR via API to ensure accurate information

Vendor Considerations: Organisational metadata in institutional systems is primarily populated and updated using the ROR API.

- Record DOI's for awarded funding
 - Ideally, link to funding bodies system to have content updated via API

Vendor Considerations: be able to consume information from funding body systems via API to update grant outcomes and additional metadata into the institutional system.

Recipe - Outputs Capture (including Data)

Research outputs are an outcome of a research activity and can come in many forms including publications (articles, books, conference papers, books chapters), grey literature such as reports, discussion papers, resource, other research artefacts (e.g. creative works and creative art), datasets and more.

Research outputs can occur at various stages in the research lifecycle. They should be accessed via a persistent link where possible which allows for findability and provides the ability to cite. Research outputs should intersect with a wide range of other PIDs to allow for accurate attribution and the ability to link to grants and funding, the project, research data and the instruments used to create it.

PIDs for research outputs should be generated by the publisher of the research output. In some cases this will be a commercial entity and in other cases a PID will be generated by the institution.

Related PIDs

DOI (for the output):

- **Created:** as the primary PID of the output. This will generally be created by the publisher; whether a commercial entity or via an institution or institutional repository
- **Consumed:** by institutional systems that collect outputs, and systems that manage and update the profile of researchers and activities such as ORCID and RAiD.

Handle:

- May be generated as the primary PID if DOI not available/appropriate

ORCID:

- **consumed** at point of manuscript submission or output publishing or release
- **contributed to** by adding outputs to profiles of researchers

ROR:

- **consumed** at point of manuscript submission or output publishing or release

DOI (other):

- DOIs of instruments may be **consumed** and **contributed** to in order to create a link between the research output and the instrument
- DOIs of grants may be **consumed** and **contributed to** in order to create a link between the research output and the associated funding
- DOIs of other research outputs may be **consumed** and **contributed to** in order to create a link between research outputs; for example linking research data and research output(s).

RAiD:

- **consumed** and **contributed** to in order to demonstrate the contribution of the research output to the project

Key Use Cases

Submission of a research output for publication:

Publishers should require each author to be identified by an ORCID wherever possible. Additionally, wherever possible, a researcher's ORCID should be linked to an ROR via the ORCID institutional integration.

Researchers should take every opportunity to include ORCIDs on submissions and within publications. They should also ensure that references to funding of the work, instruments used and associated projects are made using the appropriate PID.

Publication of an output in a journal/proceeding/book:

Once an output is published, the DOI is referenced and used by readers to access the output. The DOI is also used by the researcher(s) to cite the output.

Institutional repository/CRIS imports output record:

The institutional repository uses the DOI to import the associated metadata into its repository system. The institutional repository can also enact one or more of the following:

- Pushes the output to the author's ORCID record, pulls in the citation metrics
- Links the output to related project/award (RAiD and or funder DOI)
- Links output to other outputs (such as datasets)
- Links to instruments used.

Grant reports:

All outputs related to a funded grant can be identified via the PID and a report created.

Equipment ROI:

A report can be created on all outputs created from data generated from a specific piece of equipment and a return of investment figure generated.

Replication of research:

A dataset related to a particular research paper is able to be accessed and analysed to validate the results in the paper.

Quality Interventions

Publishers mandate authors have an ORCID, wherever possible, on the publication of an output manuscript, or dataset at point of ingestion.

Institutions may need to manually make associations in their institutional systems where an author has not been identified by an ORCID and/or when a ROR (or the correct ROR) has not been provided.

Institutions may need to manually make associations with other PIDs and/or records such as funding, other research outputs and instruments, if the association is not or cannot be made via machine to machine communication.

Key Decisions

It is **recommended** that the institution register to use the ARDCs DataCite service so they can mint DOIs for internally published outputs. Institutions may wish to develop policy, procedure or guidelines around which research outputs are provided with a PID.

It is **recommended** that the institution adopt a policy of adding other PIDs to repository records wherever possible. If your vendor doesn't permit the addition of PIDs or linking of records, assistance with requesting this functionality is available.

It is **recommended** that the institution create a policy, procedure or guideline which mandates that all authors on research outputs should have an ORCID and that ORCIDs should be added to all research publications.

System Capabilities

The primary system for storing metadata about research outputs is generally the institution repository. However, research data may be stored in a different system and the institution may use a separate system for researcher profiles where metadata about research outputs is stored. It is **recommended** that the primary "source of truth" for research outputs metadata be institutional repositories.

The system should be able to store different PIDs for different content types, for example ORCIDs for persons and DOIs for publications and datasets and equipment.

Vendor Considerations: Systems should be able to store PIDs for different content types and be able to link records using PIDs.

The system should be able to import records via APIs, and PIDs associated with those outputs should be able to be linked to the relevant records.

Vendor Considerations: When importing records using APIs, any associated PIDs which are recorded in the institutional system should be able to be identified and associated with the imported record.

Vendor Considerations:

- Systems should be able push data to ORCID and pull data from ORCID using PIDs to match persons and populate records.
- Systems should be able to read and write to/from ORCID when data is updated in the institutional repository system and not rely on a prompt from the researcher.

Recipe - Samples and Specimens

Recommendation to the Institutional Stakeholder Action Group: This topic was raised as a priority, but recommend this section be retained as a place holder for the development of guidance for institutions and other organisations on Samples and Specimens. This is a diverse and perhaps domain specific topic, so may need more deliberation than is possible within the scope of this working group. It is challenging to recommend a common approach. The audience for this approach might also be different to some of the usual PID stakeholders, with most sample/specimen systems being operated by facilities, institutes or centres that exist within or related to larger institutions.

Identifying research samples and specimens in a consistent and standardised manner can be a complex endeavour as it involves a hugely disparate range of workflow stages and entities, and of products, systems, and platforms that are used to curate the samples/specimens.

As an example, biological tissue samples may be collected in containers that are pre-identified with the suppliers' codes, and implantable/attachable identification chips/tags also have their own systems of coding. Each of these systems may be incompatible or schematically-unrelated to the other systems. When researchers commence their planning for data collection and collation, the coding of specimens and samples may reflect conditions and parameters that are germane to both the work, and intuitive and necessary for the identification workflows, as well as reflecting the idiosyncrasies and features that are specific to particular disciplines.

At a more broad level, using persistent identifiers such as the International Generic Sample Number (IGSN) may be infeasible at the coalface, where the quantities and/or the ephemerality of the samples/specimens challenge the adoption across the board of these systems as the primary method of identification.

As a consequence one of the biggest challenges for the use of specimen and sample identifiers is to standardise how they are developed for each stage of a project life cycle, how these identifiers can be carried from one stage to another, and how they can be more universally moved between different curatorial platforms. Additionally, which entities within an organisation are the sources of truth regarding the metadata for different projects' samples/specimens needs to be defined, and may include more than one entity depending on the sample type (e.g. different entities for biological and geological samples).